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The Einstein Equivalence Principle as a First-Order Functional Isomorphism

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E-mail: diego.roldan@ucuenca.edu.ec**Keywords:** Equivalence principle; Einstein equivalence principle; local inertial frames; jet bundles; quasilocal observables; General Relativity**Abstract**

The Einstein Equivalence Principle (EEP) is often glossed as “local indistinguishability” between gravitation and acceleration. Yet two influential readings pull in opposite directions: Pauli’s infinitesimal criterion is formally exact but operationally unrealizable, whereas Norton’s finite-region criterion restores empirical relevance only by introducing context-dependent thresholds for when curvature effects count as negligible. We argue that unless the admissibility conditions defining “local” are made explicit, the indistinguishability slogan becomes methodological rather than empirically testable. We therefore propose a First-Order Functional Isomorphism (FFI) reading: at any event P one can construct local inertial coordinates such that $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$. The point is not to re-derive the normal-form theorem, but to isolate its precise logical role within the EEP and to separate it from operational admissibility clauses tacitly built into indistinguishability-based formulations. On this reading, the exact geometric content of the EEP is exhausted at first order. Higher-order jet data—beginning with $j_P^2(g)$ and generically extending beyond—encode curvature and other discriminators that cannot be eliminated by coordinate choice. Under minimal coupling, nongravitational laws assume their special-relativistic normal form at P , while departures arise at higher order. This separation clarifies why tidal diagnostics and other quasilocal procedures delimit practical equivalence without constituting violations of the principle, and sharpens what high-precision free-fall experiments do—and do not—establish. The resulting picture reveals a structural tension: the EEP is mathematically exact only at the level of first-order structure, whereas any realizable localization procedure is necessarily quasilocal and constrained by finite resolution, and plausibly—under extreme conditions—by quantum localization bounds. By isolating the strictly first-order geometric core of the principle, this formulation also provides a principled framework for addressing several recurring objections in the literature concerning the operational meaning and empirical scope of locality.

1 Introduction*1.1 Exposition of the Equivalence Principle*

The Einstein Equivalence Principle (EEP) occupies a foundational role in the conceptual architecture of General Relativity. It is commonly expressed through the slogan that “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration.” While pedagogically powerful, this formulation conceals significant ambiguities concerning the meaning of locality and the logical scope of indistinguishability claims. In the literature, two influential interpretations illustrate this tension: Pauli’s infinitesimal criterion secures formal exactness at a mathematical point, whereas Norton’s finite-region approach restores operational meaning only by introducing context-sensitive admissibility thresholds. The resulting landscape suggests that what is often presented as a single principle in fact intertwines distinct geometric and operational components.

This paper argues that the exact geometric content of the EEP can be cleanly isolated at the level of first-order jet structure. We propose a First-Order Functional Isomorphism (FFI) reading, according to which the principle asserts that at any event P one can construct local inertial coordinates satisfying $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$. By explicitly separating this first-order geometric statement

from additional admissibility assumptions concerning experimental realizability, we clarify both the mathematical precision and the empirical scope of the EEP.

The Equivalence Principle (EP) is supported by an extensive experimental program, with different formulations constrained by different classes of tests. In particular, modern tests of *free fall*—including Eötvös-type torsion balances and the space-based *MICROSCOPE* mission (science operations 2016–2018; final results published in 2022), as well as complementary cold-atom interferometry tests—have verified the *universality of free fall* (WEP/UFF), commonly parameterized by the Eötvös ratio η , at the 10^{-15} level (with the strongest bounds at this level coming from *MICROSCOPE*) [43, 44]. This 10^{-15} figure, however, should be understood as attaching most directly to WEP/UFF; it does not by itself constitute a uniform “ 10^{-15} confirmation” of the full Einstein Equivalence Principle (EEP), which additionally involves local Lorentz invariance (LLI) and local position invariance (LPI), nor of the Strong Equivalence Principle (SEP), which concerns self-gravitating bodies and genuinely gravitational experiments [49].

Despite this remarkable empirical robustness—especially for WEP/UFF—a substantial literature suggests that EP-type statements can be placed under pressure in specific theoretical settings, particularly within quantum mechanical and quantum field-theoretical frameworks [3–5]. In any case, in Einstein’s original formulation, the EP served as the conceptual cornerstone and foundational heuristic in the development of General Relativity [13, 17, 49].

The present work fully acknowledges this empirical robustness. Nevertheless, as in the case of quantum theory—where unparalleled experimental success coexists with persistent foundational debates—empirical confirmation alone does not exhaust the conceptual analysis of a physical principle. The aim of this study is to provide a careful conceptual refinement of the Equivalence Principle by making explicit what the EEP genuinely secures: a first-order local normal form for nongravitational physics at an event (capturable as $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$ under minimal coupling), rather than an unconditional claim of absolute indistinguishability once higher-order (curvature/tidal) structure is operationally accessible. To this end, we distinguish the exact differential-geometric content of the local-inertial construction from the operational and methodological restrictions that are often tacitly built into slogans such as “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration.”

Following a widely used pedagogical and conceptual tradition, one often encounters a *gloss* of the Einstein Equivalence Principle according to which, if the EEP is to count as a genuine “principle of equivalence,” it must entail an (absolute) *indistinguishability* between the effects of acceleration and gravitation within domains that are “sufficiently small” [see, e.g., 29, 32]. On this gloss—frequently presented in slogan form—it is said that *no local experiment* can discern the nature of the “field.” We argue, however, that this reading—*unlike the standard, empirically substantive EEP* understood as the conjunction of WEP+LLI+LPI for nongravitational physics in freely falling laboratories [49]—generates a structural tension: either (i) it is challenged, in principle, by higher-order discriminators (e.g. tidal effects or suitably refined gradient-sensitive diagnostics), or (ii) it retreats into a methodological rule in which “locality” is fixed by admissibility clauses that, if left implicit, risk becoming circularly immunizing (i.e. they exclude *by stipulation* precisely those procedures that would discriminate in finite-resolution domains).

Accordingly, our target throughout is the *absolute-indistinguishability gloss*, not the standard EEP itself; our aim is to isolate the exact first-order geometric core and to make explicit the additional admissibility assumptions required to interpret “local experiments” operationally.

1.2 From “Equivalence” to a Functional-Isomorphism Reading

More precisely, at any event P on a smooth Lorentzian manifold, one can introduce a local inertial frame (e.g. via Riemann normal coordinates) such that

$$g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}, \quad \partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}(P) = 0, \quad \text{equivalently} \quad \Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0, \quad (1)$$

so that, for minimally coupled nongravitational fields in a metric theory, their laws can be written, at P , in special-relativistic form [9, 46, 49]. However, this normal-form reduction is intrinsically *first order*: curvature (and thus tidal structure) is encoded in the second-order jet of the metric (equivalently, in $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$) and cannot be eliminated by any coordinate choice. Consequently, the slogan “no experiment can distinguish acceleration from gravitation” is not a theorem of the geometry; it becomes defensible only after one restricts the admissible class of “local experiments” so as to exclude precisely those procedures sensitive to higher-order structure.

To make this “first-order” content explicit, we will understand the local-inertial construction in terms of *jet data*. In Riemann normal coordinates at P , the metric has Minkowski value and

vanishing first derivatives, so that the *first jet* of g at P matches that of η :

$$j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta). \quad (2)$$

Assuming a metric theory with (standard) minimal coupling for nongravitational fields, this first-order normal form is precisely what underwrites the claim that nongravitational laws can be written in their special-relativistic form at P . Importantly, this does not eliminate *second-order* structure: curvature is encoded in $j_P^2(g)$ (equivalently, in $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$) and therefore remains available, in principle, to sufficiently refined quasilocal diagnostics.

In this sense, the relevant “equivalence” is best understood as a first-order structural correspondence (normal-form/1-jet matching), not as an all-orders identity between accelerated and gravitational situations. This motivates the interpretive shift adopted in this paper. Instead of treating the EEP as asserting a literal identity between accelerated and gravitational situations, we read it as asserting a *functional isomorphism at first order*: within a sufficiently small domain (in an explicitly controlled approximation sense), nongravitational dynamics admits a mapping to its special-relativistic form via the local normal-form construction. On this reading, the existence of physical discriminators does not constitute a “violation” of the EEP; rather, it marks the boundary between the principle’s first-order geometric content and the higher-order (or implementation-dependent) structure that the principle was never entitled to erase.

This reframing is not a mere semantic preference. It directly targets the epistemic vulnerability of the traditional “absolute indistinguishability” rhetoric: if one insists on defending the principle by progressively narrowing “local experiments” to exclude tidal, gradient, or energetic diagnostics, the claim risks becoming self-immunizing. The functional-isomorphism reading preserves what is genuinely secured by differential geometry while keeping the empirical question of higher-order and operational discriminators explicitly open.

In the sections that follow, we argue that if one insists on formulating the EP/EEP as a thesis of *absolute local indistinguishability* (rather than as the first-order functional correspondence articulated above), then one is naturally led to putative “falsifications” driven by higher-order geometric and operational diagnostics—tidal/curvature-sensitive procedures, quasilocal gradients, and implementation-dependent energetic bookkeeping—that lie outside the strict first-order normal-form content. The functional-isomorphism reading is introduced precisely to keep this boundary explicit: it preserves what differential geometry genuinely guarantees at first order while treating such higher-order discriminators as delimiting the principle’s domain rather than as straightforward violations.

Definition (First-Order Functional Isomorphism; FFI). We say that the EEP holds at an event P in the *FFI* sense iff there exist local inertial coordinates at P such that

$$j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta), \quad (3)$$

i.e. $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}(P) = 0$ (equivalently, $\Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0$). Under minimal coupling, this suffices for nongravitational laws to assume their special-relativistic normal form at P , while all curvature/tidal structure resides in $j_P^2(g)$ and beyond.

Minimal coupling (working criterion). To make the preceding “under minimal coupling” clause explicit, we adopt the following standard working criterion. A nongravitational field theory is *minimally coupled* to (M, g) iff its curved-spacetime action depends on the metric only through the replacements $\eta_{\mu\nu} \mapsto g_{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial \mapsto \nabla$, together with the invariant volume element $\sqrt{-g} d^4x$, and contains *no explicit curvature couplings* (e.g. terms such as $R\phi^2$, $R_{\mu\nu}A^\mu A^\nu$, $R F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$, $R_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}F^{\mu\nu}F^{\rho\sigma}$, etc.). Under this assumption, the local inertial construction at P yields the special-relativistic normal form of the matter field equations *at* P .

Counterexample (non-minimal coupling). If explicit curvature couplings are present, the local inertial construction does *not* in general restore the special-relativistic normal form even at an event. For instance, a scalar field with a non-minimal curvature coupling satisfies

$$(\square - m^2 - \xi R)\phi = 0, \quad (4)$$

where ξ is a dimensionless constant. In a local inertial frame at an event P one can set $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}(P) = 0$, but the term $\xi R(P)\phi(P)$ does not vanish unless $R(P) = 0$ or $\xi = 0$ (the minimally coupled case in this example). Thus, the *first-order* geometric normal form ($j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$) is not by itself sufficient: the inference to a special-relativistic normal form for matter laws requires the additional physical assumption of minimal coupling.

What FFI adds beyond the normal-form fact. The existence of local inertial coordinates with $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}(P) = 0$ is a standard geometric normal-form fact. The contribution of the FFI reading is *not* to re-derive that fact, but to make explicit two pieces that are typically left implicit in “local indistinguishability” glosses:

1. **A scope (admissibility) clause.** FFI isolates the *exact* first-order content (the 1-jet matching) and treats any appeal to “local experiments” as involving an additional, explicitly stated restriction on admissible procedures—namely, a choice of target observables \mathcal{O} , an apparatus scale L , and a resolution/tolerance δ .
2. **A principled delimiter/violation distinction.** On the FFI reading, a putative discriminator counts as a *domain delimiter* (rather than a “violation”) whenever it accesses higher-order structure—in particular, information encoded in $j_P^2(g)$ (curvature/tidal effects) or in quasilocal implementation variables—since such diagnostics lie outside what the first-order correspondence ever secured. By contrast, a genuine *violation* would require failure of the first-order special-relativistic normal form at P (for minimally coupled nongravitational laws), or failure of the additional bridge principles (LLI/LPI implementations) that are required to interpret the EEP operationally.

In this way, the FFI reading turns a slogan into a scope-controlled statement: it preserves the exact geometric core while making the operational domain and the status of higher-order discriminators explicit.

1.2.1 What FFI is for: a bookkeeping role (not a new theorem) The existence of local inertial coordinates with $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}(P) = 0$ is a standard normal-form fact. We therefore do *not* present FFI as a new geometric result. Its role is *bookkeeping*: it fixes the *exact* first-order geometric core and thereby cleanly separates three further ingredients that are otherwise conflated in sloganized “local indistinguishability.”

(i) Logical dependence. FFI(P) by itself is a coordinate-existence statement; the inference to special-relativistic *matter* normal form at P requires an additional physical assumption:

$$\text{FFI}(P) + \text{MC} \implies \text{SR normal form for minimally coupled nongravitational laws at } P, \quad (5)$$

whereas $\text{FFI}(P) + \neg\text{MC}$ fails generically (explicit curvature couplings give counterexamples).

(ii) Admissibility for “local experiments”. Any empirical “local indistinguishability” claim is indexed by a triple $\mathcal{E} = (\mathcal{O}, L, \delta)$ (target observables, protocol scale, tolerance). Without (\mathcal{O}, L, δ) the slogan has no determinate test content.

(iii) Diagnostic classification. With this bookkeeping in place, discriminators fall into two conceptually distinct kinds: *domain delimiters* (those whose leading dependence is on higher-order geometry $j_P^2(g)$ or on quasilocal implementation variables), versus *genuine violations* (those that break the FFI + MC inference at P , or that violate the empirical EEP commitments WEP/LLI/LPI). We use this classification throughout to prevent the first-order geometric core from being overextended into a universal ban on discriminators.

Remark (relation to prior work). This FFI formulation may also serve as a reusable formal template for extended special-relativistic scenarios previously developed by the authors [38], without presupposing any such extension here.

1.3 Versions and Standard Formulations of the Equivalence Principle

Modern presentations distinguish three main formulations (or “flavours”) of the Equivalence Principle, which clarify both its empirical scope and operational meaning [49].

The **Weak Equivalence Principle** (WEP) asserts the universality of free fall: freely falling test bodies follow trajectories independent of their internal composition, a property commonly parameterized by the Eötvös ratio η . Current tests constrain $|\eta|$ down to the 10^{-15} range [44].

The **Einstein Equivalence Principle** (EEP) strengthens the WEP by requiring that, in *freely falling laboratories*, the outcomes of all *non-gravitational* experiments be independent of the laboratory’s velocity and spacetime position. Equivalently, the EEP is the conjunction of (i) WEP, (ii) local Lorentz invariance (LLI), and (iii) local position invariance (LPI) [49].

The **Strong Equivalence Principle** (SEP) extends the EEP further, encompassing gravitational experiments and self-gravitating bodies, where gravitational binding energy contributes non-negligibly to the total mass–energy [49].

In standard formulations, the operational content of the EEP is typically tied to two idealizations: (i) a *locality requirement*, whereby tidal effects are neglected at the scale of the laboratory, and (ii) a restriction to *non-gravitational* experiments. The present work focuses on the EEP and **interrogates** how these idealizations shape—and potentially limit—its epistemic status.

1.4 On the Operational Domain of the EEP

Standard textbook formulations often present the EEP in terms of *freely falling local laboratories*, emphasizing that nongravitational physics locally reduces to special relativity in local inertial frames [7, 29, 49]. This emphasis is methodologically natural: free fall provides the most direct route to local Lorentz frames and to the *cleanest* separation between inertial artifacts and curvature effects available within the classical framework.

However, it is useful to distinguish this *canonical formulation choice* from the broader heuristic contrast that historically motivated the principle. In his early discussions, Einstein explicitly compared uniformly accelerated systems with systems statically supported in a gravitational field [14, 15]. His 1916 refinement does not so much eliminate that contrast as it sharpens its *domain*: the analogy can be sustained only within sufficiently small regions, since realistic gravitational fields are inhomogeneous and tidal effects become observable beyond the local limit [17].

In this sense, the restriction to freely falling laboratories functions as a practical idealization for stating the EEP with maximal clarity, rather than as a claim that acceleration–gravity comparisons have no principled role outside that setting [7, 49]. This distinction will be important below, because it helps separate (i) the canonical pointwise normal-form content of the EEP from (ii) additional operational questions about what measurement procedures are tacitly admitted or excluded when one appeals to “local experiments”.

Nothing in this section alters the standard statement of the EEP in terms of local inertial frames; the point is to keep analytically distinct the canonical formulation and the acceleration–gravity heuristic that historically motivated it [14, 15, 17, 49].

1.5 Interpretive Debates and Axes of Discussion

Beyond its strong empirical support—including the final *MICROSCOPE* bounds on WEP/UFF and the *ALPHA* collaboration’s first observation of gravitational free-fall effects on antihydrogen—the Equivalence Principle (EP) remains the subject of sustained interpretive debate [2, 44]. Contemporary discussions span several partially independent axes: (i) the relation between the EP’s *operational* content and any alleged *ontological* claim about the nature of gravitation [6, 30]; (ii) the coexistence of non-equivalent “flavours” of the EP (WEP/EEP/SEP) and the risk of conflating them in foundational arguments [8, 49]; (iii) the proper understanding of “locality”—as an infinitesimal point-identity or as an approximate finite-region criterion—and the conditions under which curved-spacetime physics may be said to be “locally special relativistic” [20, 27, 32]; and (iv) broader extensions where quantum considerations or alternative gravitational frameworks may constrain or reinterpret EP-type statements [10, 18]; see also [37, 40]. Relatedly, recent work proposes extending the EEP to *quantum reference frames*, defining *quantum locally inertial frames* in which the metric appears locally Minkowskian even for superpositions of gravitational fields [23]. See also a recent nonrelativistic-quantum formulation of the EEP (including the free-fall/inertial equivalence in a uniform field and the role of $m_g = m_i$) [42].

To make axis (i) more concrete, note that “geometry-first” readings treat gravitation as spacetime curvature [9], whereas field-theoretic approaches describe gravity as a massless spin–2 field on a flat background [19, 48]. In either idiom, the empirical coincidence $m_i = m_g$ is typically taken as an *input* rather than derived, leaving its explanatory status open [30, 49]. Relatedly, horizon thermodynamics and quantum-field phenomena in curved spacetime are frequently cited as loci where strong readings of the EP face significant theoretical pressure [25, 45].

The present work sits primarily within axes (i)–(iii). We argue that much of the apparent resilience of the traditional “absolute indistinguishability” rhetoric arises from a tacit restriction of the admissible class of experiments, rather than from the differential-geometric content of the EEP itself. Accordingly, we separate (a) the exact first-order normal-form content (capturable as $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$ in suitable local frames), (b) the inevitable quasilocality of realizable measurements, and (c) higher-order geometric and operational diagnostics—including tidal/curvature-sensitive procedures and implementation-dependent energetic constraints—that can distinguish acceleration from gravitation once one leaves the strictly first-order idealization.

Scope clarification (what is *not* being challenged). Nothing in this paper is intended to deny the *standard* Einstein Equivalence Principle as it appears in the contemporary literature—namely, the conjunction of WEP, LLI, and LPI for nongravitational physics in freely falling laboratories—nor its substantial empirical support. Our target is the stronger *absolute-indistinguishability gloss* often attached to the EEP in informal slogan form (“no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration”) when the admissibility conditions on “local” and on the relevant class of experiments are left implicit. The aim is to isolate the principle’s exact first-order structural core and to prevent its extrapolation into a universal ban on higher-order (quasilocal) discriminators.

2 Conceptual and Historical Foundations

2.1 Evolution of Einstein’s Criterion (1907–1916)

The introduction established the empirical solidity of EP-type claims and motivated a scope-sensitive reading. The present section provides a historical and conceptual baseline by tracing how Einstein’s own formulations shift from a broadly stated equivalence (1907–1911) to an explicitly local principle (1916).

Einstein first articulated the guiding idea in 1907—later recalled as “the happiest thought of my life”—by emphasizing that a freely falling observer does not experience weight and by proposing a “complete physical equivalence between a gravitational field and the corresponding acceleration of the reference system” [14]. In 1911 he stated, in similarly strong terms, that a system K at rest in a *homogeneous* gravitational field and a system K' in uniform acceleration are “physically exactly equivalent,” in the sense that “the laws of nature take the same form in both” [15]. As formulated in these early texts, the claim is not yet presented with an explicit restriction to a small spacetime neighborhood, nor with a systematic separation between first-order inertial effects and higher-order (tidal) structure.

A key feature of the 1907–1911 heuristic is Einstein’s reliance on a *homogeneous gravitational field* as the gravitational counterpart of uniform acceleration. In operational terms, homogeneity amounts to treating the gravitational field strength as spatially constant, $\vec{g}(\mathbf{x}) = \vec{g}_0$, so that $\nabla\vec{g} = 0$ and tidal signatures—manifested as geodesic deviation—are, by construction, absent [15, 30]. This idealization is methodologically convenient: it isolates the “inertial” aspects of weight/acceleration and sustains the analogy with uniformly accelerated frames. However, it is physically non-generic: as a global configuration, perfect homogeneity does not represent the field of a localized source ($\propto 1/r^2$) and typically requires non-localized idealizations such as infinite planar symmetry [30, 32]. Consequently, the empirical scrutiny of the early EP proceeds not through the literal realization of such fields, but via derived consequences—such as the gravitational redshift—where inhomogeneities are experimentally negligible for the scale of the phenomenon [14, 15].

By 1915, when Einstein introduced the final form of the field equations, the equivalence principle was no longer presented as an independent axiom or an *unrestricted identity claim*. Rather, it became closely intertwined with the program of General Relativity: the emphasis shifted to the generally covariant field equations and to showing that they recover Newtonian gravity in the weak-field limit [16]. In 1916, Einstein made the limitation of the equivalence idea explicit: within a sufficiently small region, an accelerated frame may be treated as equivalent to a homogeneous gravitational field, but this equivalence cannot be extended to larger domains because realistic gravitational fields are inhomogeneous [17]. This marks the transition from the early heuristic of complete equivalence to a local (idealized) principle: beyond the small-region limit, tidal effects become observable and the curvature of spacetime—quantified by the Riemann tensor

$R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}$ —provides the **invariant discriminator** between genuine gravitation and mere acceleration.

Conceptually, this restriction to a sufficiently small domain is not merely a rhetorical retreat; it yields a concrete methodological gain. First, it removes the dependence on a globally homogeneous gravitational field—an idealization that suppresses gradients by fiat and has no direct physical realization for localized sources—and replaces it with an explicitly *scale-controlled* criterion that is compatible with realistic, inhomogeneous fields [30, 32]. Second, it transforms “equivalence” from an unqualified identity claim into an approximation scheme with a principled error budget: in local inertial constructions, departures from the special-relativistic form are governed by curvature through terms of order $O(RL^2)$ (and, operationally, tidal signatures scale with separation), so that the domain of applicability can be stated in terms of the size L of the laboratory relative to curvature scales [9, 46]. Finally, the local reformulation dovetails with the emerging geometric framework of general relativity, where the relevant structure is encoded in the possibility of constructing local inertial frames and in the tensorial characterization of curvature that remains once first-order inertial effects are removed [46, 49].

This historical trajectory reveals a clear *contraction of scope* that helped secure the formal coherence of General Relativity. Between 1907 and 1916, Einstein progressively restricted the Equivalence Principle from a broad heuristic equivalence between acceleration and gravitation to a statement with a strictly local domain of validity: within regions where $O(RL^2)$ effects are negligible, non-gravitational laws reduce to their special-relativistic form when expressed in local inertial coordinates [14, 15, 17, 49]. In this refined interpretive framework, the EEP is best understood not as a global, all-orders identity claim, but as a conceptually sophisticated **heuristic anchor** for spacetime geometry.

Having outlined the canonical local formulation, we now proceed to interrogate the conceptual vulnerabilities of an Equivalence Principle anchored primarily in the locality criterion. Specifically, we shall examine how this reliance on an ever-shrinking domain risks rendering the principle's core claims either operationally vacuous or immunised against empirical scrutiny

2.2 From Heuristic Generality to a First-Order Principle: Idealization, Domain Delimitation, and the Risk of Triviality

A persistent interpretive mistake in the reception of the equivalence idea is to treat Einstein's early heuristic comparisons as licensing a blanket thesis of *absolute indistinguishability*. The target of the present discussion is not Einstein's own heuristic use of the equivalence idea, but a stronger *sloganized* reading that is often adopted in later presentations: the claim that “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration” without an explicit specification of what “local” and “experiment” are allowed to mean.

In 1907 and 1911, Einstein motivates the principle by juxtaposing uniform acceleration (well-defined in special relativity) with a *homogeneous gravitational field* and formulates the comparison in strikingly strong terms of physical equivalence [14, 15, 30]. However, as a matter of physical content, the homogeneous-field model does not “control” discriminators in the experimental sense; it *suppresses* them by idealization. In the pre-geometric (largely Newtonian) sense in which a uniform field is introduced, imposing $\nabla\vec{g} = 0$ removes tidal/gradient signatures by assumption, thereby eliminating precisely those effects that would discriminate (in sufficiently resolved finite domains) between gravitation sourced by localized matter and mere acceleration in flat spacetime [30, 32]. In this respect, the early heuristic is conceptually clarifying but evidentially limited: it exhibits a case in which certain discriminators are set to zero, rather than establishing that such discriminators cannot exist.

The crucial point is that tidal effects are not a nuisance to be “controlled away” in any empirical sense; they are the discriminators that fix the boundary of any strong, global identity claim [32, 46]. The later emergence of an explicitly *local* formulation is therefore best understood as a change in the *order* and *domain* of the claim, not as a denial of physical differences. Real gravitational fields sourced by localized matter are generically inhomogeneous; hence tidal effects provide discriminators *in principle* whenever the laboratory has nonzero extension and sufficient resolution [32, 46]. The modern geometric core of the Einstein equivalence idea is naturally first-order: one may construct local frames in which nongravitational laws take their special-relativistic form at an event, while higher-order structure (curvature/tidal content) remains and becomes accessible once one probes beyond that first-order idealization [9, 46]. In this sense, locality functions as a principled domain delimitation: it specifies the regime in which the intended correspondence is asserted, rather than “hiding” the very effects that mark its limits.

This distinction sharpens the methodological concern that motivates the present work. Difficulties arise when the EEP is formulated (or informally glossed) as the unconditional claim that *no local experiment* can distinguish gravitation from acceleration, then the empirical bite of that slogan depends crucially on what counts as a “local experiment”. Taken literally, that slogan is stronger than the standard EEP as it appears in the contemporary literature, which is formulated for *nongravitational* physics in freely falling laboratories and does not purport to eliminate higher-order curvature structure or genuinely gravitational self-interaction (issues that fall, if anything, under stronger principles such as the SEP) [49]. More generally, if “local” admissibility is fixed so as to exclude, *a priori*, precisely the gradient- or curvature-sensitive diagnostics (and, at the operational level, implementation-dependent bookkeeping such as resource/energy expenditure) that would reveal differences in finite-resolution settings, then “indistinguishability” is secured primarily by the admissibility restrictions themselves—a form of *triviality-by-idealization* rather than an independently testable physical constraint [30, 32].

Accordingly, the present paper adopts a reformulation of the EEP in terms of a *first-order functional isomorphism*. Instead of reading the principle as an all-orders identity between accelerated and gravitational situations (as suggested by some sloganized “indistinguishability”

formulations), we treat it as securing a first-order functional correspondence—namely, a local normal-form (1-jet) matching for nongravitational laws under minimal coupling. Higher-order geometric structure and operational discriminators are then understood as delimiting the scope of that correspondence, rather than as straightforward “violations.” The next subsection develops the conceptual apparatus needed to make this separation precise by distinguishing point-assigned quantities from the quasilocal procedures required for their determination.

2.3 Pointlike Phenomena vs. Computational Methods

A recurrent source of confusion in discussions of the Einstein Equivalence Principle is the failure to distinguish a quantity’s **pointwise (ontological) assignment** from the **procedures** by which it is represented, calculated, or measured. In what follows we consider *local kinematical quantities* relevant to the EEP—four-velocity, proper acceleration, higher derivatives along a worldline (e.g. jerk), and spatial gradients of kinematical fields—and, when needed, *local geometric quantities* such as curvature. These objects are typically expressed using differential operators and limiting procedures, and thus their mathematical characterization invokes an infinitesimal neighborhood $U(P)$ (or, along a worldline, an infinitesimal interval in proper time) [34, 46].

From the standpoint of differential geometry, such neighborhood-dependence does *not* imply that the relevant quantity is “non-local” in the sense of being spread over a finite region. Rather, it reflects a fact about *representation and determination*: derivatives are defined by (equivalence classes of) local behavior near P . The theory of **jet bundles** provides a precise formal encoding of this idea: the k -jet $j_P^k(\phi)$ of a field ϕ records its Taylor data at P up to order k as a fiber object over P , thereby associating higher-order variation data with a point without thereby asserting any substantive metaphysical thesis about locality [41].

For example, the four-acceleration of a timelike worldline at an event P is a vector in the tangent space $T_P M$,

$$a^\mu(P) = \left. \frac{Du^\mu}{d\tau} \right|_P, \quad (6)$$

even though any practical determination (and the standard analytic definition) appeals to a limiting procedure along the curve,

$$a^\mu(P) = \lim_{\Delta\tau \rightarrow 0} \frac{u^\mu(\tau + \Delta\tau) - u^\mu(\tau)}{\Delta\tau}, \quad (7)$$

where τ is proper time and $D/d\tau$ denotes covariant differentiation along the worldline [34, 46]. Likewise, higher kinematical derivatives such as the *jerk*,

$$j^\mu(P) = \left. \frac{Da^\mu}{d\tau} \right|_P = u^\nu \nabla_\nu a^\mu \Big|_P, \quad (8)$$

are again point-assigned vectors, while their operational extraction requires finite-resolution access to nearby points on the curve [35].

A similar point applies to spatial gradients. If a denotes the magnitude of proper acceleration and \hat{r}^α is a unit spatial direction in an orthonormal frame at P , the directional derivative $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}$ may be represented as

$$(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}(P) = \hat{r}^\alpha \nabla_\alpha a \Big|_P, \quad (9)$$

which is a local quantity defined at P (hence compatible with pointwise field ontology), even though its determination requires comparisons across a neighborhood [34, 46].

It is therefore useful to separate two levels:

1. **Pointwise assignment (ontological locality)**: in the standard formulation of general relativity, tensor fields (e.g. $T_{\mu\nu}$ and $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}$) are defined pointwise on spacetime [9, 46].
2. **Operational determination (quasilocality)**: extracting values of derivatives (and thus accessing higher-order jet data) requires finite-resolution procedures that sample a neighborhood of P in space and/or along a worldline [21, 34].

Failing to keep these levels distinct often motivates the erroneous inference that strict locality is impossible because differentiation requires “space.” The correct conclusion is weaker: neighborhoods are required for *determination* (and for the mathematical definition of derivatives), not for *pointwise assignment*. This distinction is especially clear when contrasting the connection coefficients $\Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}$ —which can be made to vanish at P by a coordinate choice—with curvature, which is tensorial, point-assigned, and cannot be eliminated by coordinates [9, 46].

The payoff is conceptual: one may preserve the **mathematical exactness** of the EEP as a pointwise normal-form claim while acknowledging that any physical realization of a “local experiment” necessarily occupies a finite spacetime region and is therefore quasilocal. This gap between pointwise structure and quasilocal access will be central in the critical analysis developed in the following sections [21].

2.4 Ontological Locality vs. Operational Determination

For the purposes of this paper, we distinguish (i) *point-assigned geometric and kinematical quantities* in the standard tensor-field formulation of General Relativity (e.g., $u^\mu(P)$, $a^\mu(P)$, $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$, and corresponding jet data), from (ii) the *operational determination* of such quantities, which is necessarily quasilocal because finite-resolution procedures require comparisons over nonzero spatial and/or temporal separations [34, 46]. This is a methodological distinction about representation and measurement, not a claim that *all* physically meaningful quantities in General Relativity are local observables in a gauge-invariant sense [47]. This two-level notion of locality will serve as the interpretive framework for assessing Pauli’s infinitesimal criterion and Norton’s regional criterion in the sections that follow.

3 Conceptual Tensions on the Notion of “Locality”

3.1 Pauli’s Criterion: Locality as the Infinitesimal Limit

The most influential mid-20th-century formalization of the Einstein Equivalence Principle (EEP) is associated with Pauli’s presentation of General Relativity, where the principle is interpreted not as a claim about “small boxes” or finite laboratories, but as a *pointwise* claim about the existence of local inertial coordinates at a single event P [33]. On this reading, “locality” is strictly identified with the idealized *infinitesimal limit* ($L \rightarrow 0$): the principle is regarded as exact at the event itself and only approximately valid in any finite neighborhood where curvature remains non-vanishing. By reducing the EEP to a property of the tangent space structure at P , the Pauli criterion secures mathematical precision at the cost of distancing the principle from its original operational context.

Mathematically, the pointwise content is expressed by the existence of **local inertial frames** (LIFs): for any event P on a smooth Lorentzian manifold, one can choose coordinates (e.g. Riemann normal coordinates) such that

$$g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}, \quad \Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0. \quad (10)$$

As emphasized in the standard literature [9, 46, 49], this establishes an **exact point-identity** in normal form: at P , nongravitational laws can be written in their special-relativistic form. In the terminology adopted above, this is precisely a *first-order* statement: in suitable local coordinates one has

$$j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta), \quad (11)$$

while higher-order structure is not eliminated.

Pauli’s pointwise strategy avoids tidal effects by restricting attention to an event. Curvature does not vanish at P in general: the Riemann tensor $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$ depends on second derivatives of the metric and remains invariantly defined even when $\Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0$ [46]. What becomes small as one shrinks a neighborhood scale $L \rightarrow 0$ is not curvature itself, but the *finite-region manifestations* of curvature. In normal coordinates, one has schematic expansions of the form

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \eta_{\mu\nu} + O(\mathcal{R}L^2), \quad (12)$$

where \mathcal{R} denotes a typical magnitude of Riemann components in an orthonormal frame at P [9, 46]. Likewise, the relative acceleration between neighboring freely falling worldlines follows from geodesic deviation,

$$\frac{D^2\xi^\mu}{d\tau^2} = -R^\mu{}_{\nu\rho\sigma} u^\nu \xi^\rho u^\sigma, \quad (13)$$

so that for separations $|\xi| \sim L$ one expects a scaling

$$|\Delta a| \sim O(\mathcal{R}L), \quad (14)$$

which also vanishes as $L \rightarrow 0$ even when $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P) \neq 0$ [9, 46].

However, this formal success generates a sharp epistemic tension. If the EEP is strictly exact only at a point of zero extension (in space and time), then no physical experiment—which necessarily requires finite duration, finite resolution, and finite separation to register change, work, or information—can be performed *within* the domain where the principle is exact. In this sense,

Pauli’s criterion preserves mathematical universality at the cost of **operational content** [32]. The EEP becomes a structural feature of the local normal form of the metric and connection rather than a directly falsifiable law of nature. This is the core of what we call the paradox of **operational vacuity**: the principle is most certain precisely where it is least applicable to realizable measurements.

3.2 Norton’s Criterion: Locality as a Finite but Small Neighborhood

In contrast to the pointwise orthodoxy, Norton has argued that Einstein’s original equivalence reasoning should not be understood as confined to an event, since its motivating thought experiments concern finite laboratories and finite procedures [30]. On this reading, “locality” refers to a **finite but sufficiently small spacetime neighborhood** in which gravitational effects are practically indistinguishable from inertial ones.

Under Norton’s criterion, the EEP becomes an **approximate regional** statement. Over a neighborhood of characteristic length L , departures from Minkowski form are controlled by curvature, schematically

$$g_{\mu\nu} \approx \eta_{\mu\nu} + O(\mathcal{R}L^2), \quad (15)$$

while tidal signatures (e.g. relative accelerations between nearby freely falling bodies) scale as $|\Delta a| \sim O(\mathcal{R}L)$ [9, 46]. On this approach, the principle acquires operational bite only once an experimental threshold is specified: if curvature-induced signatures remain below the relevant resolution, then the region counts as “locally inertial” for the purpose at hand [31].

This regional reading restores **physical relevance** by allowing experiments to occur within a finite domain, but it introduces two interrelated sources of imprecision:

1. **From identity to approximation:** once $L > 0$, the point-identity $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\Gamma^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0$ no longer suffices to characterize physics throughout the neighborhood. The EEP is no longer an exact statement about an event, but a scale-dependent approximation governed by \mathcal{R} and L .
2. **Underdetermination of “negligible”:** what counts as negligible tidal influence depends on which observables are probed and on the resolution of the procedures used. Without a principled specification of tolerances and target phenomena, “locality” risks becoming context-dependent in a way that is difficult to state as an objective geometric criterion [31, 32].

Thus, a genuine tension emerges: Pauli’s pointwise criterion preserves *formal exactness* but at the cost of operational instantiation; Norton’s regional criterion restores operational applicability but does so by recasting the EEP as an approximate, scale-dependent statement.

It is crucial to distinguish between the loose physical usage of the term “local” and its strict geometric (topological) usage. In differential geometry, a property is *local* if it holds in an open neighborhood U of a point P . In particular, a spacetime is (*exactly*) *locally flat on U* in the strong sense that there exist coordinates on U for which $g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ for all $x \in U$ *if and only if* the Riemann curvature tensor vanishes throughout that domain, $R^\alpha_{\beta\gamma\delta} = 0$ on U .

Consequently, in a generic sourced gravitational field (where curvature does not vanish), it is mathematically impossible to extend the *exact* Minkowski normal form of the metric *throughout* any finite neighborhood (in the strong sense above). What one can have instead is the *pointwise* (first-order) normal form at an event P —equivalently, the 1-jet matching $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$ —together with a controlled *approximation scheme* on finite domains in which departures scale as $O(\|\text{Riem}\| L^2)$ (and tidal manifestations as $O(\|\text{Riem}\| L)$). This is precisely why the EEP is best read as a *First-Order Functional Isomorphism* (FFI): it aligns the principle with the geometric fact that only first-order inertial structure can be eliminated at a point, while any quasilocal extension inevitably introduces curvature-driven second-order effects that delimit, rather than violate, the first-order correspondence.

Remark (Strict equivalence vs. “negligibility” in strong-field regimes). If the EP/EEP is read in a *strong* sense—as a literal physical identity between “gravitation” and “acceleration” in *finite* laboratories—then the usual retreat to claims of “negligible differences” is conceptually out of place. *Negligibility* is an epistemic predicate indexed to an experimental context (apparatus scale L , target observable, signal-to-noise, and tolerance), whereas a strong identity thesis purports to be a context-independent physical claim.

This point becomes sharper in high-curvature regimes. In Riemann normal coordinates around an event P , one has schematically

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \eta_{\mu\nu} + O(\|\text{Riem}\| L^2), \quad \text{while tidal signatures scale as } O(\|\text{Riem}\| L), \quad (16)$$

so that, for fixed experimental tolerances, increasing curvature forces the operationally admissible domain to contract (roughly $L \ll \|\text{Riem}\|^{-1/2}$) [9, 46]. In other words, the strong reading would demand a finite-domain indistinguishability that is *stable* under increases in curvature, rather than one that is preserved only by tightening the “locality” idealization. If “indistinguishability” is preserved only by allowing L to collapse toward $L \rightarrow 0$ precisely when geometric discriminators become large, then what is being defended is a limiting/idealized scheme rather than a physically robust identity claim.

Moreover, the slogan “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration” is *universal* in form; accordingly, once higher-order diagnostics are admitted, the thesis is vulnerable in principle to a single realizable counterexample, while agreement in carefully engineered small-domain regimes only supports the corresponding approximation claim. As we shall argue in the following sections, the **FFI reading** is designed precisely to prevent this conceptual slide.

The next subsection clarifies how differential geometry (via jets) makes precise the separation between point-assigned structure and quasilocal determination, thereby sharpening what is at stake in both criteria.

3.3 Infinitesimal Derivation and Jets: Local Encoding without Ontological Nonlocality

As emphasized in Subsection 2.3, the tension between Pauli’s point-identity and Norton’s regional approximation is often amplified by an unexamined assumption: that if a quantity involves variation (derivatives), it must thereby “occupy” a nonzero volume. The mathematical theory of **jet bundles** provides a rigorous way to decouple the *differential order* of a quantity from its *spatial extension* [41]. This decoupling allows us to treat higher-order properties as pointwise assignments, effectively dissolving the forced choice between infinitesimal triviality and regional approximation.

In differential geometry, the k -jet of a smooth field (section) ϕ at an event P , denoted $j_P^k(\phi)$, is an equivalence class of fields that agree in their Taylor expansion at P up to order k . In this sense, a jet encodes not only the value of $\phi(P)$, but also its derivatives at P (to order k), while remaining a **point-assigned** object: it belongs to the fiber of the k -jet bundle over P [41]. Consequently, quantities such as curvature $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$ or gradients of kinematical fields $\nabla_\mu a^\nu(P)$ are naturally understood as **ontologically local** (pointwise) geometric data, even though their *construction* and *measurement* involve differential/limiting procedures.

This formalization sharpens the two-level distinction already introduced in Subsection 2.3:

- **Operational determination:** To compute or measure derivative (jet) data, one must compare values across a neighborhood (or along a worldline) with finite resolution. This is a feature of measurement and differentiation, not of the underlying ontology [34, 46].
- **Ontological encoding:** Once defined, the resulting derivative or curvature component is assigned to the event P . Higher-order jets encode how fields vary *infinitesimally* without implying that the encoded information “occupies” a finite region in the manifold [41].

Accordingly, the fact that an observable involves differential information (e.g., a radial gradient $\nabla_{\hat{r}} a$) does not disqualify it as “local” in the ontological sense. What it does imply is that *operational access* to such observables is necessarily quasilocal. This is precisely where Pauli and Norton pull in different directions: Pauli preserves the exact point-identity by restricting attention to zeroth- and first-order normal forms at P , whereas Norton insists on finite neighborhoods where operational procedures can be carried out. Jets show that point-assigned geometric structure is rich enough to include curvature and gradients, while simultaneously clarifying why the *measurement* of that structure cannot be strictly pointlike.

Remark (curvature as a point-assigned discriminator). If “local” is taken in the differential-geometric sense of *point-assigned invariants* (as opposed to point-supported measurement procedures), then there exist point-assigned quantities with discriminative content between “mere acceleration” in flat spacetime and genuine gravitation in curved spacetime. The central example is the Riemann tensor. In a local inertial frame at an event P one can always eliminate first-order inertial effects (e.g. set $\Gamma^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0$), but one cannot eliminate curvature: $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$ is invariantly defined and governs geodesic deviation [9, 46]. In particular, for a Rindler congruence in Minkowski spacetime one has $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta} = 0$, whereas for static observers in

Schwarzschild spacetime the tidal components in an orthonormal frame scale as $R_{\hat{0}\hat{r}\hat{0}\hat{r}} \sim GM/r^3$ (up to conventional sign and frame choices). Therefore, the EEP guarantees at most a *first-order* local normal form (1-jet matching) at P ; it does not identify accelerated and gravitational situations at the level of *second-order* (curvature) structure [9, 46, 49]. Of course, the operational determination of curvature components is still quasilocal, requiring finite separations and finite resolution.

Remark (against a stronger relational reading). One could press the operational point further and adopt a stronger thesis, namely that no observable admits a genuinely pointwise instantiation and that all observables are essentially relational, ineliminably tied to finite neighborhoods. The present work does *not* assume this stronger stance. Within the standard geometric framework of General Relativity—where tensor fields and their jet data are point-assigned—it already suffices to note that *strictly pointlike operational procedures are unrealizable*. This alone limits the empirical scope and discriminative power of strong sloganized readings of the EEP, without committing to any denial of ontological locality [41, 46, 47].

4 Critical Analysis of Pauli and Norton

4.1 Critique of Pauli: Exactness at the Cost of Operational Vacuity

As discussed in Subsection 3.1, a Pauli-style reading ties the EEP to the strict pointwise (infinitesimal) claim that, at any event P , one can choose coordinates such that

$$g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}, \quad \Gamma^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0. \quad (17)$$

Here $\Gamma^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0$ is a *normal-form* statement (coordinate dependent), whereas the invariant content is carried by curvature: $R^\alpha_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$ need not vanish even though first-order inertial artifacts can be eliminated at P [9, 46]. In jet language, the pointwise construction amounts to matching first-order data,

$$j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta), \quad (18)$$

while leaving second-order structure (curvature/tides) untouched.

The difficulty is not mathematical coherence but **operational content**. Pointwise exactness does *not* entail pointwise experimental realizability. Any empirical procedure requires finite duration and finite resolution: information is registered via interactions extended in proper time, and derivative- or curvature-sensitive quantities are accessed through comparisons across nonzero separations (spatial and/or temporal) [21, 34, 35]. Even where one writes pointwise expressions (e.g. power $P = dE/d\tau$, work, or rates of change), operational access requires finite intervals and finite displacements; schematically,

$$W = \int_\gamma \mathbf{F} \cdot d\mathbf{x}, \quad \Delta E = \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau_2} P d\tau, \quad (19)$$

which cannot be implemented as strictly point-supported procedures with $d\mathbf{x} = 0$ and $d\tau = 0$.

Accordingly, Pauli's criterion secures maximal formal exactness precisely in a regime that cannot host point-supported measurements. In this sense the EEP, so construed, risks becoming **operationally vacuous**: it is most certain exactly where no realizable experimental procedure can instantiate its domain. The principle then functions primarily as a structural fact about local normal forms on differentiable manifolds (supplemented, in physical applications, by assumptions such as minimal coupling for nongravitational fields), rather than as a freestanding hypothesis with direct, pointwise test content [32, 46, 49].

4.2 Critique of Norton: From Point-Identity to Approximate Regional Criterion

To restore empirical applicability, Norton argues that Einstein's equivalence considerations were intended to apply not to a single event, but to a **finite (though small) neighborhood** in which gravitational effects are practically indistinguishable from inertial ones [30, 31]. This move, however, shifts the EEP from an *exact point-identity* to an *approximate regional criterion*. The content of the principle is thereby reformulated: it is no longer defined by the existence of a local inertial coordinate system at P , but by the claim that, over a region of characteristic size L , curvature-induced effects remain below an admissible threshold.

In practice, such a regional reading inevitably introduces scale-dependent tolerances. One may write schematic bounds such as

$$|g_{\mu\nu} - \eta_{\mu\nu}| < \epsilon, \quad \|\text{Riem}\| L^2 < \delta, \quad (20)$$

where ϵ and δ encode the resolution and tolerances relevant to the class of phenomena under investigation [9, 46]. Moreover, the most direct operational signature of curvature is tidal relative acceleration, governed by the geodesic deviation equation:

$$\frac{D^2 \xi^\mu}{d\tau^2} = -R^\mu{}_{\nu\rho\sigma} u^\nu \xi^\rho u^\sigma. \quad (21)$$

For separations $|\xi| \sim L$, one expects a tidal discriminator of order $|\Delta a| \sim O(\|\text{Riem}\| L)$ [46]. Hence, “negligibility” is not a purely geometric predicate: it depends on *which observable* is being probed (metric deviations vs. tidal accelerations vs. higher-order diagnostics), on the apparatus scale L , and on the resolution of the operational procedures.

The core issue is therefore not that Norton’s reading is “merely subjective,” but that it is **underdetermined without an explicit specification of observables and tolerances**. If the EEP is glossed as a general “indistinguishability in small neighborhoods” without stating what counts as admissible sensitivity, the principle risks becoming **elastically true** by shifting the meaning of “small enough” to match the application [31, 32]. Norton restores operational relevance, but only by turning the EEP into a scale-dependent approximation whose domain of validity is not fixed uniquely by the geometry alone, but must be supplied by the experimental and phenomenological context.

4.3 Strictly Local Experiments as Idealized Limits

The tension between Pauli and Norton points to a deeper lesson: **strictly pointlike experiments are operationally unrealizable**. All real experiments—from Eötvös-type balances to atom interferometers and space-based tests—occupy finite spacetime regions and require finite durations; they therefore probe neighborhoods $U(P)$ over timescales $\Delta\tau$, even when designed to minimize sensitivity to curvature [21, 34]. For this reason, “locality” in operational contexts is best understood as an **idealized limit** that guides approximation schemes, not as a physically instantiated domain.

In practice, calling an experiment “local” amounts to adopting an approximation scheme: one neglects curvature-induced corrections to the relevant observables at the scale L of the apparatus. Depending on the quantity of interest, this may correspond to ignoring metric deviations of order $O(\|\text{Riem}\| L^2)$ and/or tidal signatures scaling as $O(\|\text{Riem}\| L)$. Operationally, locality is thus the regime in which available procedures cannot yet resolve curvature effects with adequate **signal-to-noise ratio**. In this sense, the EEP is not a description of what *is* at an ideal point, but a statement about what is *indistinguishable* within a finite-resolution neighborhood.

4.4 Comparative Evaluation: Mathematical Exactness vs. Empirical Discriminative Power

The divergence between Pauli and Norton exhibits a genuine trade-off (Table 1). Pauli preserves **formal exactness** by restricting the EEP to a pointwise normal form; Norton restores **operational applicability** by construing “local” as a finite neighborhood in which curvature signatures are below relevant thresholds. Each gains something essential, and each faces a complementary limitation: Pauli’s reading risks operational vacuity, while Norton’s reading requires explicit (and physically motivated) tolerances and target observables to avoid indeterminacy.

Feature	Pauli (Pointwise)	Norton (Regional)
Mathematical status	Exact normal form at P	Scale-dependent approximation
Domain	Event ($L \rightarrow 0$ idealization)	Finite neighborhood ($L > 0$)
Operational instantiation	Not point-supported	Implementable (with tolerances)
Dependence on context	Minimal at the level of geometry	Explicit via observables/tolerances

Table 1. Pauli- and Norton-style readings of “locality” in the EEP.

This work positions its strategy in the gap between these readings by combining two ideas already established above. First, ontological locality is preserved: the relevant geometric and kinematical quantities (including higher-order invariants) are point-assigned objects in the standard differential-geometric framework [41, 46]. Second, operational determination is necessarily quasilocal: empirical access to derivatives, gradients, and curvature requires finite separations and finite resolution [21, 34]. This separation prepares the ground for the paper’s central interpretive move: rather than maintaining a sloganized thesis of absolute “local indistinguishability,” the EEP will be treated as securing a *first-order* correspondence (a local normal form / 1-jet matching for nongravitational laws under minimal coupling), with higher-order structure and operational discriminators understood as delineating the principle’s scope rather than as straightforward “violations” [9, 46, 49].

5 Experiments, Observables, and Quasilocality

5.1 Quasilocal Experiments and the Limits of Inference to Strict Locality

A common misconception in experimental gravity is that successful null results in high-precision free-fall tests (e.g. Eötvös-type experiments or the *MICROSCOPE* mission) establish the Einstein Equivalence Principle (EEP) “at a point.” This matters because, in Riemann normal coordinates about an event P , first-order deviations vanish by construction, while curvature enters at second order; hence any finite-domain comparison inevitably incurs $O(\|\text{Riem}\| L^2)$ corrections (with tidal manifestations scaling as $O(\|\text{Riem}\| L)$). Strictly speaking, such experiments primarily constrain violations of the *Weak Equivalence Principle*/universality of free fall (WEP/UFF), typically via bounds on the Eötvös ratio η , and they do so only *over finite experimental domains*: an apparatus of characteristic size L operating over a finite duration $\Delta\tau$ can establish, at best, that relevant differential signatures (tidal, gradient, or composition-dependent effects) remain below an instrumental threshold δ within that domain [43, 44, 49]. Any inference from these quasilocal bounds to a strict pointwise claim additionally presupposes theoretical bridge principles (e.g. minimal coupling for nongravitational physics, and appropriate implementations of LLI/LPI), which are not themselves read off from a single null result.

The inferential step from *quasilocal* null results to *strictly pointlike* “indistinguishability” is therefore unjustified. Experiments probe neighborhoods, not mathematical points, and the suppression of curvature manifestations as $L \rightarrow 0$ depends on which observable is used. In normal-coordinate expansions around an event P , deviations of the metric from Minkowski form scale as

$$g_{\mu\nu}(x) = \eta_{\mu\nu} + O(\|\text{Riem}\| L^2), \quad (22)$$

where $\|\text{Riem}\|$ denotes a curvature scale at P . By contrast, operational tidal signatures such as relative accelerations between nearby freely falling bodies, governed by geodesic deviation,

$$\frac{D^2 \xi^\mu}{d\tau^2} = -R^\mu{}_{\nu\rho\sigma} u^\nu \xi^\rho u^\sigma, \quad (23)$$

scale as $|\Delta a| \sim O(\|\text{Riem}\| L)$ for separations $|\xi| \sim L$ [9, 34, 46]. Thus, what experiments establish is a **finite-resolution bound** on curvature manifestations at scale L , not the truth of an exact point-identity as an operational claim.

A useful methodological point is that success in arbitrarily small *quasilocal* regimes does not, by itself, constitute evidence for what holds in the strictly *local* idealization. In GR, any realizable experiment has $L > 0$ and therefore constrains only finite-resolution manifestations of curvature (tidal and higher-order effects) within that domain; it does not operationally instantiate the limit $L \rightarrow 0$, nor does it automatically license inferences about the exact content of that ideal limit. An instructive analogy comes from special relativity: empirical agreement for timelike motions with v arbitrarily close to c is not evidence for the physically distinct null regime associated with $v = c$ (which massive bodies do not attain). Likewise, agreement in arbitrarily small quasilocal tests ($L > 0$) shows only that discriminators can be made *unresolved* at the adopted scale, not that they are *absent* in the idealized strictly local limit. In short: “arbitrarily small” is still not “strictly local,” just as “arbitrarily close to c ” is not the case $v = c$ for massive bodies.

5.2 Quasilocal Observables Breaking Practical Equivalence: Radial Gradients

To probe beyond first-order kinematics in finite domains, one can consider observables sensitive to differential structure, such as the **radial gradient of proper acceleration** $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}$ for a congruence of observers. A key caveat, however, is that gradients alone do *not* imply curvature: even in flat Minkowski spacetime, accelerated congruences exhibit nontrivial acceleration gradients. What can carry discriminative content is the **functional and geometric package** relating local acceleration, its spatial variation, and (when present) curvature—i.e. information ultimately encoded in higher-order jet data of the metric and of the relevant kinematical fields [34, 46].

Remark (derived fields and jet order shifts). The scalar a is not a primitive field but a *derived* quantity: $a^\mu = u^\nu \nabla_\nu u^\mu$ depends on the congruence u^μ and on the connection, and therefore on first derivatives of the metric [34, 46]. Accordingly, even if one matches the *numerical value* of $a(P)$ across two scenarios, the way a *varies* in a neighborhood can be constrained differently whenever the metric’s higher-order jet data differ. In particular, curvature—which is encoded in $j_P^2(g)$ and captured invariantly by $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$ —can enter the consistency conditions governing the spatial and temporal behavior of derived kinematical fields (and their higher derivatives), beyond what is fixed by matching only 0-jet or 1-jet kinematical data [9, 46].

Definition (radial gradient). Let u^μ be the four-velocity field of a congruence and $a^\mu := u^\nu \nabla_\nu u^\mu$ its four-acceleration, with magnitude

$$a := \sqrt{a_\mu a^\mu}. \quad (24)$$

Given a unit spatial direction \hat{r}^μ orthogonal to u^μ at P (i.e. $u_\mu \hat{r}^\mu = 0$ and $\hat{r}_\mu \hat{r}^\mu = 1$), define the directional (“radial”) gradient of the acceleration magnitude by

$$(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}(P) := \hat{r}^\mu \nabla_\mu a \Big|_P. \quad (25)$$

Operationally, extracting $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}$ is necessarily *quasilocal*: it requires comparing acceleration readouts (or related observables) at separated points along \hat{r} within a finite laboratory domain [21, 34].

Flat spacetime: Rindler congruence. In Minkowski spacetime, consider the standard uniformly accelerated (Rindler) congruence. In units $c = 1$, observers at fixed Rindler “height” χ have proper acceleration

$$a(\chi) = \frac{1}{\chi}, \quad (26)$$

so that along the natural radial direction one finds

$$\frac{da}{d\chi} = -\frac{1}{\chi^2} = -a^2, \quad (27)$$

even though the Riemann tensor vanishes identically, $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta} = 0$ [9, 46]. Thus, $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}} \neq 0$ is compatible with *no* gravitation in the geometric (curvature) sense.

Curved spacetime: static congruence in Schwarzschild. For static observers in Schwarzschild spacetime (units $G = c = 1$), the proper-acceleration magnitude at areal radius r is

$$a(r) = \frac{M}{r^2 \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{r}}}, \quad (28)$$

with radial variation (weak-field expansion for $r \gg 2M$)

$$a(r) \approx \frac{M}{r^2}, \quad \frac{da}{dr} \approx -\frac{2M}{r^3}, \quad (29)$$

while relativistic corrections become important as $r \rightarrow 2M$ [34, 46]. In such sourced gravitational fields, tidal structure is generically present and encoded in curvature (second-order jet data of the metric) [9, 46].

How gradients delimit practical equivalence. The lesson is not that $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}$ *by itself* “detects curvature,” but that *matching* the *local* value $a(P)$ does not exhaust what can be probed in a finite domain: once one accesses spatial variation (and, more generally, higher-order structure), additional discriminators become available in principle [34, 46]. In the jet language adopted here, the EEP’s strict content concerns first-order normal forms ($j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$ in suitable local inertial constructions), whereas curvature and tidal structure reside in $j_P^2(g)$ and cannot be removed by coordinate choice [9, 46, 49]. Hence, finite-size (quasilocal) procedures can break practical indistinguishability even while the EEP’s first-order pointwise normal form remains intact.

Jet bookkeeping (what is fixed at which order). It is helpful to separate the *order* at which different comparisons are being made. Equality of the local proper-acceleration magnitude $a(P)$ fixes only the *0-jet* of the scalar field a at P (its point value). Access to the radial gradient $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}(P)$ amounts to fixing a component of the *1-jet* $j_P^1(a)$ (first-derivative data of a at P). By contrast, the invariant geometric discriminator between “mere acceleration” in flat spacetime and genuine gravitation is curvature, which resides in the *2-jet* of the metric $j_P^2(g)$ (equivalently $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta}(P)$) [9, 46]. Thus, matching $a(P)$, or even matching $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}(P)$, does not amount to matching the geometric data that encode tidal structure: it constrains only lower-order kinematical jets, while the second-order geometric jet remains free to differ.

Generic inequivalence and exceptional coincidences. Two points are crucial for avoiding a self-immunizing reading.

1. **Universal slogan vs. existential counterexample.** The slogan “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration” is *universal* (it quantifies over all admissible experiments and all relevant situations); hence *a single physically realizable counterexample* suffices to refute it, whereas agreement in specially engineered cases cannot establish it.
2. **Why equality of gradients is non-generic (jet formulation).** Matching $a(P)$ and $(\nabla a)_{\hat{r}}(P)$ amounts to matching (parts of) the lower-order kinematical data $j_P^0(a)$ and $j_P^1(a)$. But two scenarios can agree on these lower jets while differing on $j_P^2(g)$: in flat spacetime $j_P^2(g) = j_P^2(\eta)$, whereas in a sourced gravitational field $j_P^2(g) \neq j_P^2(\eta)$ in general [9, 46]. Once $j_P^2(g)$ differs, higher-order consistency conditions on the spatial dependence of a (e.g. second derivatives of a along \hat{r} , geodesic-deviation/tidal responses of nearby worldlines, or other curvature-coupled diagnostics) will generically fail to match in any finite neighborhood [34, 46]. Hence coincidences at the level of $a(P)$ and its first derivative are, at best, exceptional *jet-matching* conditions rather than evidence for a robust indistinguishability thesis.

Accordingly, the role of radial-gradient observables in this paper is precisely to make the domain boundary explicit: they are quasilocal diagnostics that can, in principle, distinguish realistic gravitational fields from mere acceleration once one goes beyond the strictly first-order idealization, without thereby turning the EEP into a false geometric theorem [9, 46, 49].

5.3 Operational Indicators: Resource Bookkeeping and Mass–Energy Expenditure

It is also useful to note a concrete implementation asymmetry: a laboratory statically supported on a planet’s surface can be kept off geodesic motion by external constraint forces (the normal force of the ground) without any necessary *onboard* mass depletion (idealizing away dissipative losses and active stabilization), whereas an otherwise isolated self-accelerating laboratory in flat spacetime typically requires sustained thrust generated by onboard resources. This contrast is not geometric but implementational: it concerns how a non-geodesic state is physically maintained.

A further operational handle on the limits of “equivalence” concerns **resource bookkeeping** required to maintain non-geodesic motion. Here one must be precise: relativistic “power” is not a scalar invariant in general; it is typically frame-dependent (e.g. dE/dt relative to a chosen observer field). What *is* invariant is the contraction of the four-force with the four-velocity. If a particle has four-momentum $P^\mu = mu^\mu$ and four-force $F^\mu = DP^\mu/d\tau$, then

$$u_\mu F^\mu = u_\mu \frac{D(mu^\mu)}{d\tau} = \frac{dm}{d\tau} u_\mu u^\mu + m u_\mu a^\mu = -\frac{dm}{d\tau} \quad (\text{signature } - + + +, c = 1), \quad (30)$$

since $u_\mu u^\mu = -1$ and $u_\mu a^\mu = 0$ [9, 34]. Thus $u \cdot F$ tracks *rest-mass change* along the worldline. (For a constant-mass particle acted on by an external force one has $u_\mu F^\mu = 0$; the depletion interpretation is appropriate for variable-mass systems such as idealized rockets, where onboard mass is converted into thrust [9, 34].)

For propulsion-supported motion (e.g. rockets), a meaningful operational indicator of *resource consumption* can be captured by a mass–energy expenditure rate along the worldline,

$$r(\tau) := -\frac{dm}{d\tau}, \quad (31)$$

interpreted as the rate at which onboard resources are converted into thrust to sustain a prescribed proper-acceleration history [9, 34].

Jet-level clarification (geometry vs. implementation). It is useful to locate this bookkeeping discriminator in the jet hierarchy. The FFI content of the EEP is a statement about the *metric* at an event—namely the first-order normal-form/1-jet matching $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$ in suitable local inertial coordinates [9, 46, 49]. By contrast, the expenditure rate $r(\tau)$ is not a claim about the jet of g at P but about the jet of additional *matter/implementation variables* (the apparatus’ internal degrees of freedom) along the laboratory worldline. Concretely, if $m(\tau)$ denotes the onboard rest mass available to be converted into thrust, then the pair $(m(\tau_0), \dot{m}(\tau_0))$ is precisely the 1-jet $j_{\tau_0}^1(m)$, and

$$r(\tau_0) = -\dot{m}(\tau_0) \iff j_{\tau_0}^1(m) \text{ encodes the local rate of resource depletion.} \quad (32)$$

Thus, even when two situations are arranged to coincide at the level of first-order *geometric* data (FFI), they may still differ at the level of first-order *implementation* data (the propulsion/support state), without thereby constituting any violation of the EEP [9, 34]. Operationally, accessing \dot{m} is still quasilocal (it requires finite-duration sampling along the worldline), just as for other derivative diagnostics [35].

Two clarifications are essential. First, $r(\tau)$ is *not* a purely kinematical invariant of a worldline independent of the propulsion model: it depends on how thrust is generated and on what is counted as “resource.” Second, comparing energetic profiles between “hovering in a gravitational field” and “accelerating in flat spacetime” inevitably imports quasilocal or global structure (supports, boundary conditions, reference observers, redshift factors, etc.) because energy itself is not a purely local scalar in generic curved spacetimes [34, 46].

Accordingly, energetic bookkeeping complements curvature- and gradient-sensitive observables: it highlights that the EEP’s pointwise first-order normal form does not entail equivalence of *implementations* of non-geodesic states once finite-size procedures, resources, and reference structures are made explicit.

Remark (energetic admissibility and the risk of stipulative triviality). Given the preceding distinctions, an outright exclusion of energetic indicators from the admissible class of “local” procedures purely to preserve an unconditional “indistinguishability” slogan is epistemically delicate. The expenditure rate $r(\tau)$ is operationally accessed through finite-resolution along-worldline information, much like other kinematical derivatives [34, 35]. Of course, since $r(\tau)$ is model-dependent, it cannot function as a purely geometric discriminator on its own. Nevertheless, excluding such indicators *by definition* in order to protect a strong indistinguishability reading risks sliding toward triviality-by-stipulation. A more careful formulation therefore keeps the separation explicit: the EEP secures a *first-order geometric normal form* for nongravitational physics at an event, but it does not entail any unconditional *energetic* equivalence between distinct physical implementations of non-geodesic motion [9, 46, 49].

6 The Risk of a Tautological Reading of the EEP

Methodological claim (locality vs. testability). Point-assigned geometric quantities (including higher-order jet data) are ontologically local, even though their operational determination is necessarily quasilocal. Hence, the slogan that “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration” is not forced by geometry alone: it depends on which measurement procedures are admitted as “local”. When admissibility is fixed so as to exclude relational or differential diagnostics, indistinguishability is secured primarily by the admissibility conditions rather than by an independent empirical constraint.

6.1 Equivalence as a Regime of Vanishing Manifestations

The preceding analysis motivates a sharpened diagnosis. The target here is *not* the standard geometric core of the EEP (as a first-order normal-form claim for nongravitational laws), but a stronger *sloganized* reading often encountered in informal presentations: the unconditional assertion that “no local experiment can distinguish gravitation from acceleration” without an explicit account of what “local” and “experiment” are permitted to mean.

On that sloganized reading, the EEP can become **trivial by stipulation**: once “locality” is defined so as to exclude, *a priori*, precisely those observables and procedures capable of discriminating gravitation from acceleration, indistinguishability is secured primarily by the admissibility restrictions themselves rather than by an independent empirical constraint.

Two familiar interpretive routes make the structure of this risk clear. On Pauli’s infinitesimal reading, the EEP is treated as an exact *point-identity* obtained from the local normal form of the metric and connection; formal exactness is preserved, but strictly pointlike experiments are operationally unrealizable. On Norton’s regional reading, locality is tied to a finite neighborhood in which curvature manifestations are deemed negligible relative to a tolerance; operational applicability is restored, but the content becomes explicitly scale- and context-dependent, since one must specify thresholds and admissible observables (Sections 3.1–3.3). In both cases, the sloganized move from “first-order correspondence” to “unconditional indistinguishability” is not warranted by geometry alone.

The resulting closure can be stated schematically as follows:

1. **Admissibility restriction:** An experiment is counted as “local” only if it is confined to a neighborhood small enough that curvature manifestations remain below a chosen tolerance (e.g. metric deviations $O(RL^2)$ and/or tidal signatures $O(RL)$ remain unresolved at the relevant resolution).

2. **Sloganized EEP (operational gloss):** Within such “local” experiments, gravitational and inertial effects are said to be indistinguishable.
3. **Closure:** The indistinguishability follows because the admissible class has been delimited so as to exclude, *by construction*, precisely the procedures (gradient-, curvature-, or implementation-sensitive diagnostics) that would reveal a difference in finite-resolution domains.

In this sense, the EEP risks functioning not as a locally falsifiable empirical hypothesis but as a **methodological rule** for a normal-form construction: it guides how to set up local inertial descriptions while restricting attention to observables that, by stipulation, do not register the higher-order structure that marks the limits of the correspondence. This is closely aligned with Ohanian’s dilemma: either the principle is exact only at a point (hence operationally empty), or it is applied to finite regions where it becomes approximate and context-dependent [32]. The deeper point is not that the EEP is a literal logical tautology, but that an *absolute indistinguishability* gloss can be rendered *resistant to local challenge* by the way “local experiment” is delimited.

The same pattern appears when energetic bookkeeping is bracketed. If one focuses exclusively on first-order kinematics at P and excludes operational indicators tied to finite-resolution procedures (such as gradients or resource-consumption rates), then one blinds the analysis to asymmetries that arise as soon as the experimental domain has nonzero extension. The slogan is then protected by admissibility, not established by physics.

Recognizing this **triviality-by-stipulation** reframes the research program of the present work. Rather than seeking an unattainable “perfect equivalence” in the limit where manifestations vanish, we focus on the **discriminative content** of higher-order, yet point-assigned, geometric structure (jets) and on how such structure becomes accessible through quasilocal operational procedures. The physically significant information lies not in the vanishing limit, but in the differential structure that the limit suppresses.

6.2 *Synthesis: Three Routes to Triviality-by-Stipulation*

The preceding discussion isolates three mechanisms by which an *absolute-indistinguishability* gloss can become difficult to challenge in practice:

1. **Definitional (admissibility):** “local experiment” is delimited so as to exclude, *a priori*, precisely those relational or differential procedures (e.g. gradient- or curvature-sensitive diagnostics) that would discriminate gravitation from acceleration.
2. **Operational (point idealization):** exact validity is tied to a strictly pointlike regime that is not physically realizable as an experimental domain, so that the strongest form of the claim lacks direct operational instantiation.
3. **Extrapolative (domain overreach):** quasilocal null results ($L > 0$) are informally taken to warrant conclusions about the strict $L \rightarrow 0$ idealization, even though such inference is not licensed by the experimental domain itself.

Remark (auxiliaries and empirical content). These mechanisms need not render the EEP meaningless. They clarify, instead, how a principle can function as a powerful *methodological constraint* while remaining comparatively resistant to direct local falsification once “locality” is fixed by idealization and auxiliary admissibility clauses. This diagnosis aligns with general lessons about auxiliary assumptions, domain restrictions, and the assessment of empirical content [12, 26, 36].

6.3 *Implications: Limits of Strictly Local Falsification*

The preceding analysis clarifies why a *strictly pointlike* falsification of the EEP is not the appropriate evidential target. Instead, the limits of equivalence-type claims can be summarized in four convergent points:

1. **Ontological locality vs. operational determination:** Many discriminators (e.g. higher-order jet data, curvature diagnostics, directional derivatives) are *point-assigned* in the ontological sense, yet their *determination* is necessarily quasilocal, since finite-resolution procedures require comparisons across nonzero separations (spatially and/or along proper time). Strict pointwise *measurement* is therefore an idealization supported only as a limiting notion, not as a realizable experimental procedure [34, 41].

2. **Quantum constraints on localization (optional reinforcement):** Independent quantum-localization considerations suggest that pushing the $L \rightarrow 0$ idealization arbitrarily far is not merely technologically difficult but conceptually unstable: sufficiently sharp localization requires large momentum transfer and energy concentration, with associated gravitational backreaction [1, 11, 22, 28].
3. **Higher-order geometric structure beyond first-order normal forms:** Matching only the first-order normal form at an event (e.g. $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha}(P) = 0$ in suitable coordinates) does not exhaust local geometric content. Curvature (and operational tidal signatures such as geodesic deviation) is encoded in higher-order structure and is, in principle, accessible through sufficiently refined quasilocal procedures [9, 34, 46].
4. **Energetic bookkeeping for non-geodesic implementations:** When one compares *implementations* of non-geodesic motion (e.g. hovering or sustained acceleration), operational resource accounting can supply additional discriminators (e.g. a mass–energy expenditure rate $r(\tau)$). Such indicators are not purely kinematical invariants: they depend on propulsion/support models and on the reference structure used to define and compare “energy” [9, 34].

Taken together, these points support a methodological conclusion consistent with the paper’s scope-oriented strategy: the EEP is most securely understood as a **first-order structural constraint** guiding local normal-form constructions for nongravitational physics, rather than as an experimentally instantiated identity asserted at a physically realizable point [17, 49].

7 Ultimate Scope and Limits

7.1 Quantum Constraints on the Notion of Local Experiments

The mathematical idealization of the infinitesimal limit ($L \rightarrow 0$) that underwrites Pauli’s point-identity reading of the EEP encounters a widely discussed *operational* obstruction at the **Planck scale**, $l_P \simeq 1.6 \times 10^{-35}$ m. Classical differential geometry presupposes a smooth manifold in which localization may be pushed arbitrarily far. By contrast, quantum mechanics suggests that attempting to probe ever smaller spacetime regions requires ever larger momentum transfer, schematically $\Delta p \sim \hbar/L$, and hence ever larger energy concentration. In the limit, the associated gravitational backreaction becomes non-negligible, suggesting that the very notion of a “local inertial frame” becomes ill-defined at the scales where the $L \rightarrow 0$ idealization is intended to reside.

A standard semiclassical estimate proceeds as follows. If an interaction is localized to a region of linear size L , one expects a characteristic energy scale

$$E \sim c \Delta p \sim \frac{\hbar c}{L}. \quad (33)$$

Associating to this energy an effective Schwarzschild radius,

$$r_s \sim \frac{2GE}{c^4} \sim \frac{2G\hbar}{c^3 L}, \quad (34)$$

one finds that $r_s \sim L$ at $L \sim \sqrt{2} l_P$ (up to order-unity factors), where $l_P = \sqrt{\hbar G/c^3}$ is the Planck length. The operational moral is that attempts to push localization far below the Planck scale plausibly induce strong gravitational backreaction (and in some scenarios collapse), thereby undermining the assumed classical background on which the localization procedure is defined [1, 11, 28].

Two clarifications are important. First, this is not a theorem of quantum mechanics alone: it relies on combining quantum localization requirements with gravitational backreaction, and is therefore best read as a semiclassical, order-of-magnitude constraint on operational procedures [22, 24, 28]. Second, what it supports is not a definitive ontological claim about the nature of spacetime, but a crucial epistemic point: *strictly pointlike experimental localization* is, at minimum, conceptually fragile beyond some regime. Consequently, the limit $L \rightarrow 0$ should be treated as a mathematical idealization rather than a physically instantiated laboratory domain; every realizable test is necessarily quasilocal [11, 22].

Importantly, this does not establish a definitive ontological thesis about what spacetime *is*; rather, it reinforces the **epistemic** point developed in this work: the “local laboratory” required by strictly pointlike readings of the EEP is not an empirically accessible domain. Any realizable test is necessarily quasilocal, and as one approaches the Planck regime, the very notion of a smooth

point-event becomes an idealization whose operational meaning is increasingly **underdetermined** [11, 22].

Interpreting “local” as an infinitesimal notion does not weaken the EEP; it removes an operational ambiguity. Read as a first-order functional isomorphism (a 1-jet matching), the principle remains formally exact while remaining consistent with quasilocal discriminators (e.g. gradients) and with quantum limits on localization.

If the Planck length sets a lower bound on operational spacetime resolution, then the infinitesimal limit $L \rightarrow 0$ —in which pointwise formulations of the EEP are formally exact—lies outside the domain of experimental physics. Accordingly, the EEP should not be read as asserting a literal coincidence of physical states, but as an *effective* first-order functional isomorphism: a 1-jet matching of the metric (and, under minimal coupling, of nongravitational laws) at an event, with curvature residing in $j_P^2(g)$ and beyond.

Remark (local falsifiability and explicit domains). Because every operational determination is unavoidably quasilocal and the $L \rightarrow 0$ idealization becomes physically untenable near the Planck scale, a thesis of *absolute* local indistinguishability is deprived of strictly local operational falsification conditions. Its empirically assessable content must therefore be articulated through explicit domains of applicability and tolerances—i.e., quasilocal regimes where higher-order signatures are bounded rather than physically eliminated. Absent such clauses, the indistinguishability claim risks functioning as a methodological restriction on admissible experiments rather than as a testable physical assertion.

7.2 A Tension at the Quantum Frontier: The EP as a Classical Organizing Principle

A methodological *irony* arises from the role of the EEP in the architecture of modern physics. The Equivalence Principle functions as a key bridge from Special to General Relativity: it motivates the geometrization of gravitation and the introduction of local inertial structure. Yet the strict pointlike (infinitesimal) idealization in which Pauli’s formulation is formally exact coincides precisely with the regime where classical General Relativity is expected to break down and yield to a quantum theory of gravity. In this domain, attempts at arbitrarily sharp operational localization are widely argued to become conceptually unstable, suggesting that the point-identities of the EEP may be emergent, coarse-grained features rather than fundamental ones [22, 28, 39].

This is not a logical contradiction, but it is a methodological tension: the EEP is most precise in a regime where the operational meaning of “point” becomes least secure. If spacetime microstructure is discrete, fluctuating, or otherwise non-classical, then the tangent-space picture that underlies point-identities may best be understood as an emergent, coarse-grained description rather than a fundamental one [22, 39]. This reinforces the central claim of the present work: the EEP is extraordinarily successful as a *classical* organizing principle, but its reliance on strict locality is an idealization whose physical interpretation has limits.

In this sense, the EEP should not be read as a literally realizable, all-orders equivalence “in physics” so much as a formally exact *infinitesimal* correspondence: it holds *as if* acceleration and gravitation were locally indistinguishable at the level of the first-order normal form (the FFI content), i.e. at the 1-jet matching $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$, while the operational accessibility of that strictly local limit is precisely what becomes fragile under quantum-localization considerations.

For present purposes, the key point is modest: the point-idealization that makes certain formulations of the EEP exact should not be conflated with an operationally realizable regime.

7.3 Reframing the Equivalence Principle: Structural Core and Domain-Limited Content

In light of the tensions between mathematical exactness, operational vacuity, and quantum-localization constraints, we propose a scope-sensitive re-evaluation of the EEP. The evidence assembled in this work suggests that the *absolute-indistinguishability gloss* on the EEP is not best treated as a **stand-alone, universally falsifiable dynamical law**. Rather, it functions more reliably as a **heuristic anchor** and a **first-order structural constraint** for the local normal-form construction that links gravitational physics to the geometry of the spacetime manifold.

Under this reinterpretation, the Pauli–Norton dilemma is softened without being denied:

- As a **structural requirement**, the EEP demands that gravitational theory admit local frames in which nongravitational laws reduce to their special-relativistic form, thereby preserving compatibility with established flat-spacetime physics (capturing Pauli’s insistence on local normal forms).

- As a **heuristic anchor**, it explains why geometrization is natural, while acknowledging that discriminative physics in any realizable setting lies in quasilocal access to higher-order structure (curvature, gradients, and operational bookkeeping), not in the idealized limit where such effects are suppressed (capturing Norton’s motivation for empirical relevance).

On this view, the EEP functions as conceptual **scaffolding** for the architecture of General Relativity: indispensable in motivating the local normal-form strategy, yet not to be overextended into a universal ban on discriminators once higher-order and operational structure becomes accessible. This is the core of the *first-order functional-isomorphism* reading developed here: what is secured is a local structural correspondence for nongravitational laws under minimal coupling, while higher-order geometric and operational signatures mark the **natural boundary** of that correspondence rather than constituting an *a priori* failure of the principle [17, 49].

8 Conclusions

We have defended a scope-sensitive refinement of the Einstein Equivalence Principle (EEP) that preserves its exact geometric core while resisting a common overextension into an all-orders thesis of “absolute local indistinguishability.” The guiding idea is simple but often left implicit: differential geometry guarantees a *first-order* local normal form, whereas the operational content of any realizable “local experiment” is unavoidably quasilocal. Once these two facts are kept distinct, several familiar interpretive tensions become tractable rather than paradoxical.

(i) What the EEP strictly secures

The exact geometric normal-form fact often conflated with the EEP can be stated as a first-order claim. At any event P in a smooth Lorentzian manifold one can choose local inertial coordinates (e.g. Riemann normal coordinates) such that $g_{\mu\nu}(P) = \eta_{\mu\nu}$ and $\partial_\alpha g_{\mu\nu}(P) = 0$, equivalently $\Gamma^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}(P) = 0$. In jet language, this is the matching $j_P^1(g) = j_P^1(\eta)$. Under the standard minimal-coupling strategy for nongravitational fields, this is precisely what underwrites the special-relativistic form of nongravitational laws at P (and only at that first-order level). Curvature and tidal structure remain encoded in $j_P^2(g)$ and cannot be removed by coordinate choice.

(ii) Functional isomorphism vs. absolute identity

These facts motivate a reinterpretation: the relevant “equivalence” is not a literal identity between accelerated and gravitational situations at all orders, but a *functional isomorphism at first order*. On this reading, the EEP licenses a local mapping of nongravitational dynamics to its special-relativistic form within a controlled approximation regime. Crucially, the existence of discriminators sensitive to higher-order structure does not constitute a failure of the EEP; it marks the boundary of what the EEP was ever entitled to erase. This shift preserves the principle’s genuine content while preventing it from being protected by an ever-narrowing admissibility clause on what counts as a “local experiment.”

(iii) Pauli, Norton, and the operational gap

The Pauli–Norton dilemma is best understood as an artifact of conflating (a) point-assigned geometric structure with (b) point-supported operational procedures. Pauli’s infinitesimal criterion secures maximal formal exactness by restricting attention to the pointwise normal form, but strictly point-supported experimental procedures are not physically implementable: information acquisition, rates, and differential diagnostics require finite duration and finite separation. Norton’s regional criterion restores operational relevance by moving to finite neighborhoods where curvature manifestations are below a tolerance, but it thereby turns the principle into a context-dependent approximation unless the target observables and tolerances are made explicit. Jet-bundle language allows one to retain ontological locality (jet data are assigned to P) while acknowledging the quasilocal character of operational determination.

(iv) Empirical relevance without overreach

High-precision tests—notably of WEP/UFF—constrain equivalence-type violations only over finite experimental domains characterized by apparatus scale L and duration $\Delta\tau$. Such null results support the relevant equivalence statements *in that quasilocal regime*, but they do not by themselves warrant the stronger claim of pointlike indistinguishability. The additional inferential step to a strict $L \rightarrow 0$ conclusion requires bridge principles (e.g. minimal coupling and appropriate implementations of LLI/LPI) and a careful account of which higher-order diagnostics are excluded or included.

(v) *Methodological upshot: content, auxiliaries, and “immunization”*

The core methodological risk we identified is not that the EEP is a logical tautology, but that an *absolute-indistinguishability* gloss can become difficult to challenge once “local experiment” is defined so as to exclude, by stipulation, the very procedures that would reveal higher-order differences. Framed instead as a first-order structural constraint plus an explicit domain-of-applicability clause, the EEP retains clear explanatory value while remaining honest about where discriminators enter (tidal structure, gradients, quasilocal bookkeeping, and other implementation-dependent constraints).

Outlook

Several extensions are immediate. First, the functional-isomorphism reading can be formalized by stating the EEP as an explicit condition on the local normal form of minimally coupled field equations and by tracking how departures scale with higher-order jet data. Second, the analysis can be carried over to the SEP, where self-gravitating systems and genuinely gravitational experiments sharpen the distinction between first-order normal forms and higher-order gravitational structure. Finally, quantum-localization arguments may be used cautiously as auxiliary support for treating the strict $L \rightarrow 0$ limit as a mathematical idealization rather than an operationally accessible regime.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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